
MÖBIUS TRANSFORMATIONS INDUCED BY ROTATIONS ON THE THREE-SPHERE *

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***ABSTRACT:** Via the stereographic projection of the unit three-sphere from a pole onto the corresponding equatorial hyperplane it is induced a subgroup of the Möbius group in a three-dimensional Euclidean space. We give a geometric interpretation of any transformations of this group. Applying a quaternion algebra we describe the generated transformations by a quaternionic formalism.*

***KEYWORDS:** Möbius transformation, stereographic projection, quaternion algebra*

1 Introduction

A Möbius transformation in a N -dimensional Euclidean space \mathbb{E}^N on a real vector space \mathbb{R}^N with a standard dot product is the composition of a similarity and an inversion. These mappings are well studied in the case $N = 2$ by the complex formalism $f(z) = \frac{az + b}{cz + d}$, $a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{C}$, $ad - bc \neq 0$, where \mathbb{C} is the field of the complex numbers, in the complex plane $\mathbb{C}^* = \mathbb{C} \cup \infty$, provided by a point at infinity ∞ . The Möbius transformations are conformal maps (preserve angles between curves) and under composition of transformations they form a non-commutative group. Many applications in non-Euclidean geometries, an image processing and a geometric modeling use Möbius transformations. In [2] and [3] it is shown an algorithm for constructing a plane curve up to transformation from the subgroup of the Möbius group, induced by rotations on the unit sphere $\mathbb{S}^2 \subset \mathbb{E}^3$, centered at the origin O .

In this paper, we consider Möbius transformations in a three-dimensional Euclidean space \mathbb{E}^3 , generated by rotations on the unit sphere \mathbb{S}^3 , centered at the origin O and embedded in a four-dimensional Euclidean space \mathbb{E}^4 . The group of rigid motions on the sphere \mathbb{S}^3 coincides with the group $SO(4)$ of rotations in \mathbb{E}^4 about the origin. Any element of $SO(4)$ induces a Möbius transformation in \mathbb{E}^3 via a stereographic projection. We give an explicit representation of an arbitrary Möbius transformation corresponding to a rotation on the sphere \mathbb{S}^3 . Furthermore, it is found a quaternion formalism describing the transformations from the obtained subgroup of the Möbius group.

2 Preliminaries

Let $\varphi : \mathbb{S}^3 \setminus \{P\} \rightarrow \mathbb{E}^3$ be a stereographic projection from a pole $P \in \mathbb{S}^3$. It maps the punctured sphere $\mathbb{S}^3 \setminus \{P\}$ onto the corresponding equatorial hyperplane, identified by a three-dimensional Euclidean space \mathbb{E}^3 . If we supply \mathbb{E}^3 with a point at infinity ∞ and correspond it to the pole P , i.e. $\varphi(P) = \infty$ then $\varphi : \mathbb{S}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{E}^{3*}$, where $\mathbb{E}^{3*} = \mathbb{E}^3 \cup \infty$, is a bijective map and thus the sphere \mathbb{S}^3 is isomorphic to \mathbb{E}^{3*} .

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The non-commutative division algebra of quaternions \mathbb{H} , invented by William Hamilton, plays an important role in the groups of rotations $SO(4)$ and $SO(3)$ about the origin in \mathbb{E}^4 and \mathbb{E}^3 , respectively. The Hamiltonian algebra of quaternions $\mathbb{H} = \{(a, b, c, d); a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{R}\}$, where \mathbb{R} is the field of real numbers, is a four-dimensional real algebra with base elements $\mathbf{1} = (1, 0, 0, 0)$, $\mathbf{i} = (0, 1, 0, 0)$, $\mathbf{j} = (0, 0, 1, 0)$, $\mathbf{k} = (0, 0, 0, 1)$ and multiplication rules $\mathbf{i}^2 = \mathbf{j}^2 = \mathbf{k}^2 = \mathbf{ijk} = -1$, $\mathbf{ij} = -\mathbf{ji} = \mathbf{k}$. We can identify \mathbb{H} by the four-dimensional real vector space \mathbb{R}^4 . The properties of quaternions and their applications are known from [4] and [5]. If $w = (a, b, c, d) \in \mathbb{H}$ is a quaternion, we denote by $\mathcal{S}_w = a \in \mathbb{R}$ the real part of w . The quaternions with a zero real part are called pure quaternions. The set of pure quaternions is denoted by \mathbb{H}_0 and we have the identifications $\mathbb{H}_0 \cong \mathbb{R}^3$ and $\mathbb{H}_0^* = \mathbb{H}_0 \cup \infty$. Let $\mathcal{V}_w = (b, c, d) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the vector corresponding to the pure quaternion $b.\mathbf{i} + c.\mathbf{j} + d.\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{H}_0$. Then any quaternion $w \in \mathbb{H}$ can be represented uniquely by the sum $w = \mathcal{S}_w + \mathcal{V}_w$ of a real part $\mathcal{S}_w \in \mathbb{R}$ and a vector part $\mathcal{V}_w \in \mathbb{H}_0$. The quaternion $\bar{w} = \mathcal{S}_w - \mathcal{V}_w$ is called a conjugate quaternion of w . The norm of quaternion $w = (a, b, c, d)$ is denoted by $\|w\|$ and $\|w\|^2 = a^2 + b^2 + c^2 + d^2 = w.\bar{w}$. If $w \neq 0$ then the inverse quaternion w^{-1} of w is given by $w^{-1} = \frac{\bar{w}}{\|w\|^2}$. We can identify the set of unit quaternions S^3 by the points on the sphere S^3 and let $P = (1, 0, 0, 0)$. In terms of quaternions, the stereographic projection $\varphi : S^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_0^*$ and the reverse stereographic projection $\varphi^{-1} : \mathbb{H}_0^* \rightarrow S^3$ have very simple expressions, i.e $\varphi(w) = \frac{1+w}{1-w} = (1+w)(1-w)^{-1}$, $w \in S^3$ and $\varphi^{-1}(q) = \frac{q-1}{1+q} = (q-1)(1+q)^{-1}$, $q \in \mathbb{H}_0^*$. The next two well-known propositions are expressed in terms of quaternions.

Proposition 1. *The image of the hyperplane through the origin O with a unit normal vector $a \in S^3$ under the stereographic projection $\varphi : S^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_0^*$ is:*

a) a plane through the origin O if and only if $\mathcal{S}_a = 0$;

b) a sphere with a center $p = -\frac{\mathcal{V}_a}{\mathcal{S}_a}$ and a radius r , where $r^2 = \|p\|^2 + 1$ if and only if $\mathcal{S}_a \neq 0$.

Proposition 2. *Let s_a be a reflection about a hyperplane in \mathbb{E}^4 with a unit normal vector $a \in S^3$ through the origin, $\varphi : S^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_0^*$ be the stereographic projection from the sphere $S^3 \cong S^3$ onto the hyperplane $\mathbb{E}^{3*} \cong \mathbb{H}_0^*$ and let $F = \varphi \circ s_a \circ \varphi^{-1}$ be a transformation in \mathbb{E}^{3*} . If $\mathcal{S}_a = 0$ then the transformation F is a reflection about a plane with a normal vector \mathbf{a} through the origin O . If $\mathcal{S}_a \neq 0$ then F is an inversion J_p with a pole $p = -\frac{\mathcal{V}_a}{\mathcal{S}_a} \in \mathbb{H}_0$ and a power $\|p\|^2 + 1$.*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{S}_a = 0$. Hence, $a \in \mathbb{H}_0$, $a \in S^3$ and $a^2 = -\|a\|^2 = -1$. Applying the expressions $\varphi^{-1}(q) = \frac{q-1}{1+q}$, $s_a(w) = -a.\bar{w}.a$ and $\varphi(w) = \frac{1+w}{1-w}$ of the reverse stereographic projection, the reflection and the stereographic projection, respectively, we obtain that

$$F(q) = \frac{1 - a.\frac{\bar{q}-1}{\bar{q}+1}.a}{1 + a.\frac{\bar{q}-1}{\bar{q}+1}.a} = \frac{-a^2 - a.\frac{\bar{q}-1}{\bar{q}+1}.a}{-a^2 + a.\frac{\bar{q}-1}{\bar{q}+1}.a} = \frac{-a.(1 + \frac{\bar{q}-1}{\bar{q}+1}).a}{-a.(1 - \frac{\bar{q}-1}{\bar{q}+1}).a} = -a.\bar{q}.a = a.q.a,$$

which is a reflection about a plane in \mathbb{E}^3 through O with a normal vector \mathbf{a} (see [4]). Let $\mathcal{S}_a \neq 0$. Then

$$(1) \quad F(q) = \varphi \circ s_a \circ \varphi^{-1}(q) = \frac{2.\mathcal{V}_{aqa} - (\|q\|^2 - 1).\mathcal{V}_{a^2}}{1 + \|q\|^2 + (\|q\|^2 - 1).\mathcal{S}_{a^2} - 2.\mathcal{S}_{aqa}}, \quad q \in \mathbb{H}_0^*.$$

We find that

$$a^2 = (\mathcal{S}_a + \mathcal{V}_a)^2 = \mathcal{S}_a^2 + 2\mathcal{S}_a\mathcal{V}_a + \mathcal{V}_a^2 = \mathcal{S}_a^2 - \|\mathcal{V}_a\|^2 + 2\mathcal{S}_a\mathcal{V}_a = 2\mathcal{S}_a^2 - 1 + 2\mathcal{S}_a\mathcal{V}_a,$$

$$a.q.a = (\mathcal{S}_a + \mathcal{V}_a).q.(\mathcal{S}_a + \mathcal{V}_a) = \mathcal{S}_a^2.q + \mathcal{S}_a.(\mathcal{V}_a.q + q.\mathcal{V}_a) + \mathcal{V}_a.q.\mathcal{V}_a.$$

Hence,

$$\mathcal{S}_{a^2} = 2\mathcal{S}_a^2 - 1, \mathcal{V}_{a^2} = 2\mathcal{S}_a\mathcal{V}_a = -\mathcal{S}_a^2.p, \mathcal{S}_{a.q.a} = \mathcal{S}_a.(\mathcal{V}_a.q + q.\mathcal{V}_a) = -\mathcal{S}_a^2.(p.q + q.p),$$

$$\mathcal{V}_{a.q.a} = \mathcal{S}_a^2.(q + p.q.p),$$

where $p = -\frac{\mathcal{V}_a}{\mathcal{S}_a}$. Replacing these expressions in (1), after some rearranges and simplifications we get

$$F(q) = (1 + \|p\|^2) \cdot \frac{q - p}{\|q - p\|^2} + p,$$

which is the equation of an inversion J_p with a pole p and a power $\|p\|^2 + 1$. □

The four-dimensional rotation group $SO(4)$, that preserves the sphere $\mathbb{S}^3 \subset \mathbb{E}^4$, contains two kinds of rotations: simple rotations and double rotations. In the next two sections we will represent these rotations on the sphere $\mathbb{S}^3 \subset \mathbb{E}^4$ by transformations from the Möbius group in \mathbb{E}^{3*} applying the algebra of quaternions. The complex formalism that represents the rotations on the sphere $\mathbb{S}^2 \subset \mathbb{E}^3$ in the complex plane, provided by a point at infinity, is $f(z) = \frac{a.z + b}{-\bar{b}.z + \bar{a}}$, $a, b, z \in \mathbb{C}$, $\|a\|^2 + \|b\|^2 = 1$, where by $\|z\|$ it is denoted the norm of the complex number z and \bar{z} means the complex conjugate of z . We will find the quaternion formalism for the Möbius transformations corresponding to the rotations, preserving the sphere \mathbb{S}^3 .

3 Representation of simple rotations on \mathbb{S}^3 by Möbius transformations in \mathbb{H}_0^*

A simple rotation about a rotation center O on the tree-sphere \mathbb{S}^3 leaves a plane α through O a pointwise invariant and induces in the planes β , that are completely orthogonal to α , plane rotations about centers $C_\beta = \alpha \cap \beta$. All these plane rotations have the same rotation angle θ . According to the paper [1], any simple rotation on \mathbb{S}^3 through an angle θ can be represented by the transformation $f(w) = a.w.b$, $a, b, w \in \mathbb{S}^3$, where $\mathcal{S}_a = \mathcal{S}_b = \cos \frac{\theta}{2}$. If $s_1(w) = -y.\bar{w}.y$, $s_2(w) = -z.\bar{w}.z$, $y, z, w \in \mathbb{S}^3$ are reflections about the hyperplanes in $\mathbb{E}^4 \cong \mathbb{H}$ through the origin, determined by the normal vectors y and z , respectively, then $f = s_2 \circ s_1$ and $a.y = y.b = z$.

Theorem 1. *Let $f(w) = a.w.b$, $a, b, w \in \mathbb{S}^3$, $\mathcal{S}_a = \mathcal{S}_b$ be a simple rotation on the sphere \mathbb{S}^3 through an angle θ , $\varphi : \mathbb{S}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_0^*$ be a stereographic projection and let $F = \varphi \circ f \circ \varphi^{-1}$ be the induced transformation in $\mathbb{E}^{3*} \cong \mathbb{H}_0^*$.*

a) *If $b = \bar{a}$ then the transformation F is either the identity transformation I in \mathbb{H}_0^* or a rotation about an axis $\mathbb{R}_{\mathcal{V}_a}$ through the angle θ , where $\cos \frac{\theta}{2} = \mathcal{S}_a$ and $\mathbb{R}_{\mathcal{V}_a}$ is the one-dimensional vector space, defined by the nonzero vector \mathcal{V}_a ;*

b) *If $b \neq \bar{a}$ then the transformation F is either the composition $F = J_l \circ J_p$ of inversions J_l and J_p with poles $p = \frac{\mathcal{V}_{ab}}{1 - \mathcal{S}_{ab}}$ and $l = \frac{\mathcal{V}_{a^2b} - \mathcal{V}_a}{\mathcal{S}_a - \mathcal{S}_{a^2b}}$, respectively, provided that $\mathcal{S}_a = \mathcal{S}_b \neq 0$, or the composition $F = G_z \circ J_p$, where G_z is a reflection about a plane, provided that $\mathcal{S}_a = \mathcal{S}_b = 0$.*

Proof. Let $b = \bar{a}$ and $\mathcal{V}_a = 0$. Then $a = b = 1$ and therefore $F \equiv I$. If $\mathcal{V}_a \neq 0$ then any unit pure quaternion $y \in \mathbb{H}_0$, orthogonal to \mathcal{V}_a , satisfies the condition $a.y = y.\bar{a} = z \in \mathbb{H}_0$. Hence, $f(w) = z.\bar{y}.w.\bar{y}.z = s_z \circ s_y(w)$, where s_y and s_z are reflections about the hyperplanes, defined by y and z , respectively. From Proposition 2 we find that $F = \varphi \circ s_z \circ s_y \circ \varphi^{-1} = \varphi \circ s_z \circ \varphi^{-1} \circ \varphi \circ s_y \circ \varphi^{-1} = G_z \circ G_y$, where G_z and G_y are reflections about planes in \mathbb{E}^3 . Therefore, $F(q) = G_z \circ G_y(q) = (z.y).q.(y.z) = a.q.\bar{a}$ is a rotation in \mathbb{E}^3 about an axis $\mathbb{R}_{\mathcal{V}_a}$ through the angle θ , where $\cos \frac{\theta}{2} = \mathcal{S}_a$ (see [4]).

Let $b \neq \bar{a}$ and $\mathcal{S}_a = \mathcal{S}_b \neq 0$. Hence, $\mathcal{V}_b \neq -\mathcal{V}_a \Leftrightarrow$

$$(2) \quad \langle \mathcal{V}_b, \mathcal{V}_b \rangle \neq - \langle \mathcal{V}_a, \mathcal{V}_b \rangle \Leftrightarrow 1 - \mathcal{S}_b^2 \neq - \langle \mathcal{V}_a, \mathcal{V}_b \rangle \Leftrightarrow \mathcal{S}_a^2 - \langle \mathcal{V}_a, \mathcal{V}_b \rangle - 1 \neq 0,$$

where by $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ is denoted the standard dot product in \mathbb{E}^3 . From Lemma 2.2 in [1] it follows that there exists a unit quaternion $y = \frac{a.b - 1}{\|a.b - 1\|}$ such that $a.y = y.b = z$ and $f = s_z \circ s_y$, where s_z and s_y are reflections about hyperplanes. Using (2) we obtain that

$$\|a.b - 1\|.\mathcal{S}_y = \mathcal{S}_{ab-1} = \mathcal{S}_{ab} - 1 = \mathcal{S}_a^2 - \langle \mathcal{V}_a, \mathcal{V}_b \rangle - 1 \neq 0 \Rightarrow \mathcal{S}_y \neq 0 \quad \text{and}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \|a.b - 1\|.\mathcal{S}_z &= \mathcal{S}_{a^2b-a} = \mathcal{S}_{a^2b} - \mathcal{S}_a = \mathcal{S}_{a^2}\mathcal{S}_b - \langle \mathcal{V}_{a^2}, \mathcal{V}_b \rangle - \mathcal{S}_a = \\ &= (2\mathcal{S}_a^2 - 1)\mathcal{S}_a - 2\mathcal{S}_a \langle \mathcal{V}_a, \mathcal{V}_b \rangle - \mathcal{S}_a = 2\mathcal{S}_a.(\mathcal{S}_a^2 - \langle \mathcal{V}_a, \mathcal{V}_b \rangle - 1) \neq 0 \Rightarrow \mathcal{S}_z \neq 0. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, from Proposition 2 it follows that $F = J_l \circ J_p$, where $p = -\frac{\mathcal{V}_y}{\mathcal{S}_y} = \frac{\mathcal{V}_{ab}}{1 - \mathcal{S}_{ab}}$ and

$$l = -\frac{\mathcal{V}_z}{\mathcal{S}_z} = \frac{\mathcal{V}_{a^2b} - \mathcal{V}_a}{\mathcal{S}_a - \mathcal{S}_{a^2b}}.$$

If $\mathcal{S}_a = \mathcal{S}_b = 0 \Leftrightarrow a^2 = b^2 = -1$ then $\mathcal{S}_y \neq 0$, but $\|a.b - 1\|.\mathcal{S}_z = \mathcal{S}_{a^2b-a} = -\mathcal{S}_b - \mathcal{S}_a = 0 \Rightarrow \mathcal{S}_z = 0$ and $F = G_z \circ J_p$, where G_z is a reflection about a plane, defined by $z \in \mathbb{H}_0$. \square

Corollary 1. Let $f(w) = c.w.c$, $c \in S^3$, $\mathcal{S}_c \neq 0$, $\mathcal{V}_c \neq 0$ be a simple rotation on the sphere S^3 , $\varphi : S^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_0^*$ be a stereographic projection and $F = \varphi \circ f \circ \varphi^{-1}$ be the induced transformation in $\mathbb{E}^{3*} \cong \mathbb{H}_0^*$. Then F is the compositions $F = J_1 \circ J_p = J_0 \circ J_{p''} = J_{p'} \circ J_0$ of two inversions, where

$$(3) \quad p = \frac{\mathcal{S}_c}{1 - \mathcal{S}_c^2}.\mathcal{V}_c, \quad l = \frac{2.\mathcal{S}_c^2 - 1}{2.\mathcal{S}_c^2}.p$$

and

$$(4) \quad p' = -p'' = -\frac{\mathcal{V}_c}{\mathcal{S}_c}.$$

Proof. The equalities $F = J_l \circ J_p$ and (3) follow immediately from the Theorem 1b), when $a = b = c \neq \bar{c}$ (since $c \notin \mathbb{R}$).

Another way to represent the rotation f is the product $f = f_2 \circ f_1$ of reflections $f_1(w) = -\bar{w}$ and $f_2(w) = -c.\bar{w}.c$. Also, $f = f_1 \circ f_2'$, where f_2' is the reflection $f_2'(w) = -\bar{c}.\bar{w}.\bar{c}$. Hence, according to Proposition 2, we obtain that F is the compositions $F = J_0 \circ J_{p''} = J_{p'} \circ J_0$ of inversions J_0 after $J_{p''}$ and $J_{p'}$ after J_0 , where p' and p'' are determined by (4). \square

4 Representation of double rotations on the sphere \mathbb{S}^3 by Möbius transformations in \mathbb{E}^{3*}

The double rotations in \mathbb{E}^4 about a center O , preserving the sphere \mathbb{S}^3 , leave only the point O invariant. Any double rotation has at least one pair of completely orthogonal 2-planes α and β through O , that are invariant, but they aren't a pointwise invariant. In general, the rotation angle θ in α and the rotation angle ψ in β are different.

First, we will consider the transformation $f(w) = c^2.w$ on the sphere $\mathbb{S}^3 \subset \mathbb{E}^4$, where $c, w \in S^3$, $\mathcal{S}_c \neq 0$, $\mathcal{V}_c \neq 0$. It is clear that $f = f_2 \circ f_1 = f_1 \circ f_2$, where $f_1(w) = c.w.c$ and $f_2 = c.w.\bar{c}$. According to Theorem 1a) and Corollary 1 we have that the transformation $F = \varphi \circ f \circ \varphi^{-1}$, induced by the stereographic projection $\varphi : S^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_0^*$ in \mathbb{H}_0^* , is $F = R_{\mathcal{V}_c}^\theta \circ J_l \circ J_p = J_l \circ J_p \circ R_{\mathcal{V}_c}^\theta$, where $R_{\mathcal{V}_c}^\theta$ is a rotation about an axis $\mathbb{R}_{\mathcal{V}_c}$ through the angle θ , $\cos \frac{\theta}{2} = \mathcal{S}_c$. The poles l and p of inversions J_l and J_p , respectively, are defined by (3).

Similarly, the transformation $f(w) = w.c^2$ on the unit sphere $\mathbb{S}^3 \subset \mathbb{E}^4$ is a commute product of rotations $f_1(w) = c.w.c$ and $f_2(w) = \bar{c}.w.c$. Then the corresponding transformation $F = \varphi \circ f \circ \varphi^{-1}$, induced by the stereographic projection $\varphi : S^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_0^*$ in \mathbb{H}_0^* , is $F = R_{\mathcal{V}_c}^{-\theta} \circ J_l \circ J_p = J_l \circ J_p \circ R_{\mathcal{V}_c}^{-\theta}$, where the axis of rotation $R_{\mathcal{V}_c}^{-\theta}$, the angle θ , the poles l and p of the inversions J_l and J_p , respectively, are defined as above.

Theorem 2. *Let $f(w) = a.w$, $a \in S^3$, $\mathcal{V}_a \neq 0$ be a rotation on the sphere \mathbb{S}^3 , $\varphi : S^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_0^*$ be a stereographic projection and $F = \varphi \circ f \circ \varphi^{-1}$ be the induced transformation in $\mathbb{E}^{3*} \cong \mathbb{H}_0^*$. Then F is the compositions $F = R_{\mathcal{V}_a}^\theta \circ J_l \circ J_p = R_{\mathcal{V}_a}^\theta \circ J_0 \circ J_{p''} = R_{\mathcal{V}_a}^\theta \circ J_{p'} \circ J_0$ or $F = J_l \circ J_p \circ R_{\mathcal{V}_a}^\theta = J_0 \circ J_{p''} \circ R_{\mathcal{V}_a}^\theta = J_{p'} \circ J_0 \circ R_{\mathcal{V}_a}^\theta$ of a rotation and two inversions, where*

$$(5) \quad p = \frac{1}{1 - \mathcal{S}_a} \cdot \mathcal{V}_a, \quad l = \frac{\mathcal{S}_a}{1 + \mathcal{S}_a} \cdot p, \quad \cos \theta = \mathcal{S}_a$$

and

$$(6) \quad p' = -p'' = -\frac{\mathcal{V}_a}{1 + \mathcal{S}_a}.$$

Proof. We set $a = c^2$, $c \in S^3$, $\mathcal{S}_c \neq 0$, $\mathcal{V}_c \neq 0$ and we find that $\mathcal{S}_c^2 = \frac{1 + \mathcal{S}_a}{2}$, $\mathcal{V}_c = \frac{\mathcal{V}_a}{2 \cdot \mathcal{S}_c}$.

Applying the last relations and using the equalities (3) and (4) we get (5) and (6). \square

Analogously, we have the next theorem:

Theorem 3. *Let $f(w) = w.b$, $b \in S^3$, $\mathcal{V}_b \neq 0$ be a rotation on the sphere \mathbb{S}^3 , $\varphi : S^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_0^*$ be a stereographic projection and $F = \varphi \circ f \circ \varphi^{-1}$ be the induced transformation in $\mathbb{E}^{3*} \cong \mathbb{H}_0^*$. Then F is the compositions $F = R_{\mathcal{V}_b}^{-\psi} \circ J_m \circ J_n = R_{\mathcal{V}_b}^{-\psi} \circ J_0 \circ J_{n''} = R_{\mathcal{V}_b}^{-\psi} \circ J_{n'} \circ J_0$ or $F = J_m \circ J_n \circ R_{\mathcal{V}_b}^{-\psi} = J_0 \circ J_{n''} \circ R_{\mathcal{V}_b}^{-\psi} = J_{n'} \circ J_0 \circ R_{\mathcal{V}_b}^{-\psi}$ of a rotation and two inversions, where*

$$(7) \quad n = \frac{1}{1 - \mathcal{S}_b} \cdot \mathcal{V}_b, \quad m = \frac{\mathcal{S}_b}{1 + \mathcal{S}_b} \cdot n, \quad \cos \psi = \mathcal{S}_b$$

and

$$(8) \quad n' = -n'' = -\frac{\mathcal{V}_b}{1 + \mathcal{S}_b}.$$

The transformations $f(w) = a.w$, $a \in S^3$ and $f(w) = w.b$, $b \in S^3$ in $\mathbb{E}^4 \cong \mathbb{H}$ are so called left and right transformation, respectively. Clearly, left(right) transformations form a group and every left transformation commutes with every right transformation. Also, these transformations are known as Clifford translations. Obviously, any double rotation is a product of a left and a right transformation. Hence, summarizing Theorem 2 and Theorem 3 we obtain the next theorem.

Theorem 4. *Let $f(w) = a.w.b$, $a, b \in S^3$, $\mathcal{S}_a \neq \mathcal{S}_b$ be a double rotation on the sphere S^3 , $\varphi : S^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_0^*$ be a stereographic projection and $F = \varphi \circ f \circ \varphi^{-1}$ be the induced transformation in $\mathbb{E}^{3*} \cong \mathbb{H}_0^*$. Then F is the compositions $F = F_1 \circ F_2 = F_2 \circ F_1$, where $F_1 = R_{\mathcal{V}_a}^\theta \circ J_l \circ J_p = R_{\mathcal{V}_a}^\theta \circ J_0 \circ J_{p''} = R_{\mathcal{V}_a}^\theta \circ J_{p'} \circ J_0$ or $F_1 = J_l \circ J_p \circ R_{\mathcal{V}_a}^\theta = J_0 \circ J_{p''} \circ R_{\mathcal{V}_a}^\theta = J_{p'} \circ J_0 \circ R_{\mathcal{V}_a}^\theta$, $F_2 = R_{\mathcal{V}_a}^{-\psi} \circ J_m \circ J_n = R_{\mathcal{V}_b}^{-\psi} \circ J_0 \circ J_{n''} = R_{\mathcal{V}_b}^{-\psi} \circ J_{n'} \circ J_0$ or $F_2 = J_m \circ J_n \circ R_{\mathcal{V}_b}^{-\psi} = J_0 \circ J_{n''} \circ R_{\mathcal{V}_b}^{-\psi} = J_{n'} \circ J_0 \circ R_{\mathcal{V}_b}^{-\psi}$ and p, l, θ, m, n, ψ are defined by the equalities (5), (6), (7) and (8).*

The transformations F , generated by the rotations $f \in SO(4)$ on the unit sphere S^3 via the stereographic projection φ , form a six-parameter subgroup of the Möbius group $\text{Möb}(3)$ in \mathbb{E}^3 . By the next theorem we give a quaternion formalism for an arbitrary element of this subgroup.

Möbius transformations in a four-dimensional Euclidean space \mathbb{E}^4 , supplied by a point at infinity ∞ , are well determined by the quaternion formalism

$$f(w) = (a.w + b).(c.w + d)^{-1}, \quad a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{H} \quad (\text{see [6]}),$$

where the matrix $M = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}$ is

assumed to be invertible and the determinant $\det \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} = \|a.d - a.c.a^{-1}.b\|^2 = 1$. The product of two Möbius transformations f_2 after f_1 with matrixes M_2 and M_1 , respectively, is a Möbius transformation $f = f_2 \circ f_1$ with a matrix $M = M_2.M_1$ that is the matrix product of M_2 and M_1 .

Theorem 5. *Any Möbius transformation in \mathbb{E}^{3*} , corresponding to a rotation on the sphere $S^3 \subset \mathbb{E}^4$, can be represented by the quaternion formalism*

$$(9) \quad F(q) = (A.q + B).(B.q + A)^{-1}, \quad q \in \mathbb{H}_0, \quad A, B \in \mathbb{H},$$

where $\|A\|^2 + \|B\|^2 = 1$ and $A.\bar{B} \in \mathbb{H}_0$.

Proof. Let $f(w) = a.w.b = a.w.(b^{-1})^{-1} = a.w.\bar{b}^{-1}$, $a, b, w \in S^3$ be a rotation on the sphere S^3 . Then the corresponding Möbius transformation F in \mathbb{E}^{3*} via the stereographic projection φ is the transformation $F = \varphi \circ f \circ \varphi^{-1}$ with a matrix

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & \bar{b} \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} a + \bar{b} & \bar{b} - a \\ \bar{b} - a & a + \bar{b} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Denoting $A = \frac{a + \bar{b}}{2}$ and $B = \frac{\bar{b} - a}{2}$, we obtain (9). Moreover, it is easy to find that $\|A\|^2 + \|B\|^2 = 1$ and $A.\bar{B} \in \mathbb{H}_0$.

Conversely, let F be a Möbius transformation in \mathbb{E}^{3*} , defined by (9). Then the corresponding transformation f on the sphere S^3 via the stereographic projection φ is $f = \varphi^{-1} \circ F \circ \varphi$. That is a Möbius transformation with a matrix

$$N = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ B & A \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} A - B & 0 \\ 0 & A + B \end{pmatrix}.$$

Since $\|A\|^2 + \|B\|^2 = 1$ and $A\bar{B} + B\bar{A} = 0$ then $\|A - B\|^2 = \|A\|^2 + \|B\|^2 - A\bar{B} - B\bar{A} = 1$ and $\|A + B\|^2 = \|A\|^2 + \|B\|^2 + A\bar{B} + B\bar{A} = 1$. Hence $f(w) = a.w.\bar{b}^{-1} = a.w.b$, where $a = A - B \in S^3$, $b = \overline{A + B} \in S^3$, is a rotation on the sphere S^3 . \square

Example 1. Let $c(t) = \{t.\sin(3.t), t.\cos(3.t), t\}$, $t \in \mathbb{R}$ be a conic spiral and $f(w)=a.w.b$, where

$a = \cos \alpha + \frac{\sin \alpha}{\sqrt{3}} \cdot (\mathbf{i} + \mathbf{j} + \mathbf{k})$, $b = \cos \alpha + \frac{\sin \alpha}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot (\mathbf{i} + \mathbf{k})$, be a single rotation on the sphere S^3 .

One-parameter set of Möbius curves equivalent to $c = c(t)$ under Möbius transformations, induced by f in \mathbb{E}^3 via a stereographic projection φ , is represented on Figure 1.

Figure 1: One-parameter set of Möbius curves

Example 2. Let $c(t) = \{t.\sin(3.t), t.\cos(3.t), t\}$, $t \in \mathbb{R}$ be a conic spiral and $f(w)=a.w.b$, where

$a = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} + \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}(\cos \alpha.\mathbf{i} + \sin \alpha.\mathbf{k})$, $b = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\mathbf{i} + \mathbf{j} + \mathbf{k})$, be a double rotation on the sphere S^3 .

One-parameter set of Möbius curves equivalent to $c = c(t)$ under Möbius transformations, induced by f in \mathbb{E}^3 via a stereographic projection φ , is represented on Figure 2.

Figure 2: One-parameter set of Möbius curves

References

1. Coxeter H.S.M., *Quaternions and Reflections*, The American Mathematical Monthly, Vol.53, No.3, 1946, pp.136-146
2. Encheva R., *Family of Plane Curve in the Extended Gauss Plane Generated by One Function*, Wolfram Demonstrations Project, Published: July 8, 2013, <http://demonstrations.wolfram.com/FamilyOfPlaneCurvesInTheExtendedGaussPlaneGeneratedByOneFunc/>
3. Encheva R., *Recovering Plane Curves by One of Their Conformal Invariants*, Proceedings v.53, book 6.1, Mathematics, Informatics and Physics, Ruse, 2014, p. 22-27.
4. Koecher M., Remmert R., *Hamilton's Quaternions*. In: Numbers, J. H. Ewing, Ed., Graduate Text in Mathematics, vol. 123, Springer, New York, 189-220 (1991) .
5. Kuipers J. B., *Quaternions and rotation sequences*. Princeton University Press, Princeton, New Jersey. 1998.
6. Wilker J. B., *The Quaternion Formalism for Möbius groups in Four or Fewer Dimensions*, Linear algebra and its applications 190:99-136(1993). Princeton University Press, Princeton, New Jersey. 1998.